

THE USE OF E-GOVERNMENT SERVICES BY SMALL BUSINESSES IN MUNICIPALITIES

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Abstract

The article aimed to investigate the role of e-government in improving the services, offered to small businesses in the City of Tshwane, which forms part of the Gauteng Province. The research method, used in the article, is qualitative. The data were gathered through literature review, and conceptual analysis was employed to analyse the data. The findings established that e-government services were often not considered suitable for some businesses, due to costs and technology access challenges. In addition, some provided services were found to not be of interest to some small businesses. Under agile accessibility, the focus is on ensuring that as many diverse entities as possible make use of different forms of technology and connectivity to gain access to e-government. Diverse user needs must also be captured by noting that governmental services affect population groups both far and wide. In the City of Tshwane case, low agility means that small businesses are generally not well catered for under current e-government systems. While the current study focussed solely on the City of Tshwane, an assessment of the broader Gauteng Province's e-government efforts did help in gaining a better understanding of the larger political and administrative environment, within which e-government is set. It is, furthermore, necessary to comprehend that e-government has its challenges; thereby making improvement solutions imperative to filling the noted implementation gaps. This study, therefore, sought to further examine the e-government frameworks, institutions, and stakeholders with respect to their responsibilities in, with, and for small businesses.

Keywords: e-government services, small businesses, City of Tshwane, Gauteng Province, South African municipalities

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1. Introduction

Small-, Medium- and Micro- Enterprises (SMMEs), which are also known collectively as 'small businesses, have a vital function in any economy [1]. These businesses' value lies in their ability to be the main facilitators of innovation, employment creation, and economic growth [1]. As of 1994, there have been problems with regard to South Africa re-integrating into world markets as an economy on a global scale, whilst simultaneously aligning itself with people's expectations to transition to a successful democracy [1]. To meet the goals of job creation, economic growth, wealth redistribution, and global competitiveness, since 1995, the SMME sector has been promoted in the country [2]. The value of the SMME sector in South Africa has also been recognised through the establishment in 2014 of the new Ministry of Small Business Development. The main objective of this ministry is to enable the development and promotion of SMMEs. Most SMMEs have also established themselves as important job creators and substantially contribute to the national economy [1].

It is important to note, however, that there is no universal definition of SMME. Instead, the definition depends on the country, the industry, the number of employees, annual sales, or a combination of any of these [3]. Ardic, Myelenko, and Satane add that "the number of employees and sale volumes is probably the most accurate parameter" [4] to define SMMEs. Since the definitions of SMMEs differ across countries, there is a lack of uniform or standardised definitions for small

firms [4]. In South Africa, however, a ‘small business is officially defined in Section 1 of the National Small Business Act (NSBA 102 of 1996) as amended by the NSBA amendments (26 of 2003 and 29 of 2004). Per this Section, according to the International Leadership Development Programme [5], SMMEs are distinct and separate business entities, which include non-governmental organisations; cooperatives, which are run by a single proprietor or more than one, including subsidiaries and/or branches, if available. The “business operations of SMMEs are mainly implemented in any sector and/or subsector of the economy, as listed in Column 1 of the Schedule” [5]. SMMEs are, thus, both dynamic and diverse, and exist in various locations, forms, and sizes [5]. Understanding this dynamism and diversity of SMMEs is crucial for crafting targeted interventions for their development and growth [5]. Yet, there remains a common approach to blanket all small businesses as one, with the presumption that they all face the same challenges and needs [6]. The article explores the challenges, faced by SMMEs, and proposes that e-government services may be considered significant to support of small businesses.

Electronic government and informatisation play an important role in changing the face of traditional public service delivery, bringing much promise of enhanced efficiency and a more client-driven and customer-friendly approach. Informatisation is one of the enablers for facilitating electronic government, which can be loosely defined as the management and provision of (potentially interactive) government services using electronic technologies, primarily centred around ICTs [7]. The issues, faced by SMMEs, are discussed in this article, and e-government is seen as a framework that promotes greater non-bureaucratic service delivery assistance.

2. Materials and Methods

The research approach considered is qualitative. It stresses the socially constructed nature of reality, the intimate relationship between the researcher and what is studied, and the situational constraints that shape inquiry [8]. Such researchers emphasise the value-laden nature of the inquiry. They seek answers to questions that stress how social experience is created and given meaning. The literature review was conducted to gather information through journal articles, postgraduate dissertations, web articles, and official publications of municipalities. The resources that were used in the course of writing a literature review include policies, annual reports, integrated development plans, journal articles, institutional reports, strategies, information available on e-government portals, and websites. A literature review assists researchers in “identifying and analysing information” [9]; and also refers to the analysis of documents that contain information about the phenomenon one wishes to study [10, 11] to unpack the problem statement of this study that is: what are the challenges, faced by SMMEs, that demand e-government services for improvement in South African municipalities?. The information was analysed through conceptual analysis that according to Furner (2006:233-234), “is a technique that treats concepts as classes of objects, events, properties, or relationships” [12, 13]. The technique involves precisely defining the meaning of a given concept by identifying and specifying the conditions, under which any entity or phenomenon is (or could be) classified under the concept in question [12, 13].

3. Result

3. 1. SMME challenges in South Africa

A South African-based study found that 11.8 % of all surveyed South African SMMEs indicated the bureaucratic processes, associated with getting and/or renewing permits and licences as impediments to business growth [14]. The same factors were highlighted as imposing severe challenges in transforming SMMEs from informal to formal businesses [14]. From such findings, it is clear, that traditional means of delivering public services have come with a cost, time, and process impediments that can only be best handled by well-resourced and established businesses [14]. Other scholars previously cited similar excessive regulatory pressures, associated with licences, permits, taxes, and other compliance matters as affecting SMMEs’ general performance in and across South Africa’s municipalities [15].

The SEDA further reports that bureaucracy in government is a significant issue for SMMEs, particularly concerning regulatory concerns, related to the content of the laws, associated with

conducting a business [1]. Regulatory process challenges, related to the process of complying with set regulations, are also an issue [1]. Such regulatory pressures and challenges affect SMMEs in various ways, including making it difficult for SMMEs to formalise and further comply with governmental requirements, which further affect their access to funding [1]. Also, some claims trace the bureaucratic challenges that affect SMMEs to poor coordination amongst the governmental units responsible for managing SMME matters [1]. Bureaucracy-linked inter-departmental conflict tends to spill over into the regulatory environment; thereby affecting SMME support and resulting in SMMEs struggling to function between different departments (i.e., different departments neglect their attempts to effectively coordinate and individually address their respective SMME duties) [1]. Other challenges that impede the start-up and growth of SMMEs include:

- 1) a lack of adequate infrastructure;
- 2) skills shortages;
- 3) a lack of funding;
- 4) poor market access;
- 5) high exposure to crime [1].

Easing regulatory processes could, however, be achieved by making it easier for SMMEs to access and utilise business registration and licensing systems. Effective e-government implementation could play a particularly significant role in this endeavour, as it holds within it the possibility of easing the time, costs, and process elements, associated with the business regulation challenges, currently faced by SMMEs.

3. 2. SMME challenges in Gauteng Province

There are an estimated 783 410 SMMEs currently operating in the Gauteng Province of South Africa [16]. These SMMEs, as captured in various studies, endure various challenges. For example, a study on the financial problems that SMMEs encounter highlights how enterprises of varying sizes and forms all struggled to gain either public or private sector funding [17]. Other challenges, faced by Gauteng-based SMMEs, “included poor municipal service delivery, high compliance costs, registration and licensing complexities and high operational costs” [18].

There is also a general commonality in challenges, faced by SMMEs in Gauteng. This claim is substantiated in a document, entitled Gauteng Township Economy Revitalisation Strategy 2014-19, which summarises the major challenges, faced by SMMEs in the province into five categories. The Strategy highlights that three of these challenges relate to general SMME issues, namely struggles pertaining to financial-, market-, and/or skills-related access. The Strategy then lists poor enterprise development support as the fourth major challenge that affects SMME growth in the province [19]. The fifth challenge relates to the poor characterisation of township SMMEs, owing to their diversity and the multiple non-coherent classifications and descriptions of these entities [19]. At the metropolitan level, the CoT SMMEs are regularly exposed to all manner of combinations of these noted challenges [19].

3. 3. SMMEs in the City of Tshwane

There is an approximate total of 164 000 formal and informal SMMEs operating in the CoT [16]. These SMMEs exist at various growth stages and are exposed to several challenges that affect their growth and success. For example, studies have identified bureaucracies, associated with business registration, as challenges that discourage business formalisation and affect overall SMME growth in the CoT [20–22]. Common regulatory challenges, highlighted in all these noted studies, include limited regulatory knowledge amongst SMMEs due to skills challenges; low information transfer; and costs-, time-, and process-related issues [20–22]. Various CoT-based studies have also shown that corruption – especially pertaining to procurement-related irregularities – excludes many potential SMME suppliers from local government supply systems [20–23]. Corruption is, furthermore, seen to be amongst the main vices that make it difficult for city SMMEs to gain business support from local government, as such support is generally most directed towards a few ‘connected’ businesses [24].

Further findings indicate that CoT businesses often fail to grow, and sometimes even have to close their doors for good, due to financial access-related challenges, a lack of adequate infrastructure, skills shortages, and/or a lack of adequate governmental financial and/or non-financial support [20, 25, 26]. In addition, funding challenges amongst CoT SMMEs can be attributed to a lack of knowledge regarding sources of funding [26]. A lack of managerial, supervisory, marketing, financial, and technical skills amongst SMMEs have additionally been highlighted as contributing to the failure of many CoT-based SMMEs [20].

Another skills area that is often lacking amongst SMME entrepreneurs in the CoT is ICT usage skills [27–29]. Business competition in the CoT has, furthermore, been described as relatively protracted, demanding adequacy in skills, strategies, and resources by competing parties [21]. SMMEs, thus, often fail to compete effectively with established businesses, as, among other factors, they tend to have lower levels of skills, and resources [21] market access, and/or networking strategies [25].

SMMEs operating in the CoT have been found to often struggle to access appropriate, well-located business infrastructure [21, 26, 24]. Infrastructure-related challenges are often to blame for backyard and/or inappropriately located automotive businesses in the CoT. Closely associated with infrastructure issues is poor access to basic services [29]. Business services and operations generally depend on the availability of both basic and specialised municipal services, yet as revealed in one study, poor service provision by the CoT negatively affects business growth and success, particularly amongst SMMEs [20].

Another researcher further links poor electricity availability with challenges, associated with ICT usage amongst CoT-based female entrepreneurs [28]. As highlighted in a study, SMMEs in the CoT also face general access to technology challenges [26]. The low technology uptake and knowledge, displayed amongst CoT-based SMMEs, can, however, be described as a result of the poor funding, offered to these enterprises. Wise and Chiloane-Tsoka (2015:194) similarly assert that without adequate funding, SMMEs are not able to upgrade their existing technologies to better meet industry changes, and some SMMEs are not able to afford such technology in the first place [30].

The problems discussed, in all, be classified as problems relating to:

- 1) the general business environment;
- 2) governmental support and assistance, offered to SMMEs;
- 3) local government service delivery to SMMEs [24].

Local government is, however, expected to play a significant role in the resolution of challenges, faced by SMMEs, to promote these enterprises' development [24]. The role of local government as a key stakeholder in South Africa's general local economic development (LED) makes it accountable to and responsible for addressing SMME challenges within the general business environment [30].

Some of the main challenges, faced by SMMEs, operating in the CoT include a lack of access to:

- 1) finances;
- 2) markets;
- 3) skills;
- 4) technology;
- 5) adequate infrastructure [26].

The local government also affects SMMEs as their service provider. That is, the local government is responsible for providing SMMEs with both basic and advanced services that make it possible for businesses to function effectively [26]. As the public service provider, local government is accountable to SMMEs in respect to ensuring their access to necessary services, with challenges in this area having a negative impact on business start-up and development [30]. Understandings of local government's role in SMME development and sustainability, thus, place the municipalities as being accountable for the general support and assistance of SMMEs, and responsible for alleviating many of the challenges, faced by these enterprises.

3. 4. SMME service delivery and support mechanisms in South Africa

The challenges facing South African SMMEs, including those in Gauteng's Johannesburg and Tshwane metropolitan cities, are well-documented. across several sources [20, 28, 24]. Vari-

ous institutions and entities within the three governmental spheres have also been established to alleviate these challenges, such as the Gauteng Enterprise Propeller, and the Tshwane Enterprise Development Agency. There is, however, a consensus that SMME challenges continue to persist despite the existence of these institutions, which suggests the low effectiveness of the SMME support entities and programmes that are currently in place [22].

One of the main challenges, faced within the SMME support ecosystem in the CoT, is poor coordination amongst those entities responsible for supporting SMME development [22]. Some CoT-focussed studies, for example, have captured coordination challenges between the city and SMMEs as well as between the city and other SMME-supporting governmental entities as hampering SMME growth in the city [20, 24, 29]. This lack of coordination resulted in a low transmission of SMME policies into practices that benefitted SMMEs [22]. Thus, there is a need for governmental agencies to better coordinate toward providing real and valuable market and financial access assistance to SMMEs [22].

The SACN highlights a concern that SMME support, as well as LED in general, are seen as a departmental rather than systemic activity [31]. As a result, while municipalities have various policies in place, the effective implementation of such policies continues to be a major challenge [31]. Some of these challenges include “coordination, communication, capacity, and contextual issues surrounding policies” [32]. Siloed and uncoordinated support programmes that are poorly tailored and which are often inaccessible to targeted beneficiaries further continue to be a common cause of municipality policy failures [32]. Generally, local government services, including LED-related provisions of basic services and the support of SMMEs, have followed traditional bureaucratic approaches that are underpinned by hierarchical public administration paradigms [32]. Some scholars, however, question whether bureaucracy is an indispensable necessity in municipal policy implementation, with the view that less bureaucratic regimes could potentially result in more effective policy implementation [32]. Research has further found that any paradigm or effort that improves service delivery to businesses inevitably also improves business performance.

Between 2012 and 2014, the CoT initiated a study, aimed at assessing the relationship between the quality of municipality services in different parts of the CoT along with the performance of start-up SMMEs. It was established, that there is an association between the quality of services, offered by municipalities, and the performance of SMMEs. SMMEs that hold a positive perception of the quality of services, offered by the municipality, also generally exhibit positive business success indicators, particularly concerning profitability [20]. Conversely, businesses that hold negative perceptions of the quality of services, offered by their municipality (i.e., the CoT), tend to exhibit negative performance [20]. These findings led to the conclusion that municipal services affect the performance of SMMEs, alongside other factors, such as financing, access to the market, business knowledge, and effective strategies [20]. Other studies have established similar links, albeit in different settings [25, 33]. The recommendations made included that the CoT should improve the quality of services that it offers to SMMEs in and across all regions of the city, as this could contribute positively toward SMME success [20].

In consideration of the challenges, faced by SMMEs in the CoT, the roles that local government plays in SMME development, as well as the SMME and service delivery support models in the application, the current study explored the role of e-government in affecting the efficiency and effectiveness of SMME support. The study also aimed to identify various SMME problems and municipal LED-related support challenges that might be resolvable using e-government services. The next section, thus, focuses on the potential role of e-government in resolving SMME challenges. The section also acknowledges that e-government implementation comes with its challenges that need to be resolved before it can be successfully utilised in alleviating identified SMME challenges.

3. 5. E-government in Gauteng

In the realisation of advantages, brought by e-government for residents, businesses, and governmental units themselves, the Gauteng Provincial government has a dedicated e-government department that falls under the Member of Executive Council (MEC) of Finance and e-govern-

ment [34]. The Gauteng Department of e-Government – Strategic Plan 2020-2025 lists the province's 'five pillars of e-government' as:

- 1) Modernised ICT Infrastructure and Connectivity;
- 2) Digital platform, e-Services, and Application;
- 3) Provincial ICT oversight and governance;
- 4) ICT solutions advocacy and communication facilitated;
- 5) Ensuring that Gauteng is a hub of Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) skills [35].

These pillars fall under the province's priority of modernising public service operations [35]. As reported by [36], the province aimed to reach the 'connected presence' level of the United Nations (UN) e-government maturity model by 2020 [37]. This phase is characterised by the advanced integration of all government services that are capable of being offered online; thereby enabling a 'one-stop-shop', transactional and communication government-to-business (G2B), government-to-citizens (G2C), and government-to-government (G2G) environment [37, 38]. The Gauteng Province's e-government department concentrates on major e-government dimensions, specifically G2B, G2C, and G2G [39]. This section focuses primarily on the G2B dimension, as this is where SMMEs belong [39]. It should be noted, that in the 2017/2018 strategic year, according to the Gauteng Provincial Government e-Government Annual Report (2017/2018,) the department achieved 17 G2C sites, one G2B site, and over 300 G2G sites [39]. The G2B sites that are of importance in SMME support include 'Economic Zones', 'iKasi Labs', and 'mLabs', all of which have been designed to increase digital access and general business assistance to SMMEs [39]. Both sources report that, amongst other outcomes, the Gauteng e-government effort aims at supporting SMME start-ups and development and includes a focus on youth entrepreneurs [36, 40]. Thus, there is already a realisation that e-government contributes to an SMME developmental function in the province.

E-government efforts in the province have also occurred within the context of dedicated strategies and as spillovers from economic and technology development plans and strategies that have been formulated and implemented over time. For example, the Gauteng City-Region (GCR) e-government strategy forms a major backbone that supports the development of broadband connectivity throughout the province as a way of reducing the digital divide that affects how businesses and communities adapt to ICTs [36]. Other strategies, connected to e-government, include the Gauteng Growth and Development Strategy (GGDS), which places ICT as a major catalytic sector for industrial and technological growth; and the Transformation, Modernisation, and Reindustrialisation (TMR) programme, which sees e-government and digitalisation as indispensable in the economic modernisation of the province [41]. Furthermore, e-government plays a critical role in the modernisation of governmental services and economic operations, which are all aimed at enhancing the provinces' global competitiveness as an economic centre [41]. All these noted strategies have far-reaching aspirations, as they go beyond merely improving local service delivery to citizens and businesses and involve citizen participation in governmental affairs [36].

In 2020, a new, broader e-government strategy, namely the Strategic Plan 2020–2025, was implemented in Gauteng. This Plan recognises the GCR e-Government Strategy's paramountcy in the transformation from e-government to e-governance [35]. This Strategy's uniqueness is, thus, in its expansion of the Gauteng Province's e-government responsibilities from the provision of transaction and compliance processing systems to augmented economic and social services systems [35]. The Strategy also confirms the responsibility of provinces in establishing e-government that is backed by digital economic systems and which facilitates, amongst others, electronic commerce (e-commerce) [35]. Of note is that the Strategy highlights how digital agriculture, which also functions on the backbone of an e-government system, could transform the province's agro-based economy [35]. On the operational side, a framework to facilitate the smooth operability of e-government systems and infrastructure has also been implemented [35]. Some of these systems include the ICT Norms and Standards, the ICT Frameworks, the ICT Continuity Management Framework (CMF) and the ICT Master Systems Plan [34]. These systems have also been upgraded to ensure the systems' security of the currently available e-government systems [34].

The GCR e-government strategy additionally places the province's economic zones in the category of 'e-government development priority areas' [34]. In these zones, the enabling of e-government and digital technologies adoption is expected to have positive economic impacts on SMMEs, citizens, and established businesses alike [41]. The strategy's targeted benefits have, furthermore, been listed as promoting easier transactions between stakeholders and the provincial government and/or its related entities, improving governmental responsiveness to service requests, and bettering service delivery quality [41].

The province further asserts that, in the long run, e-government rollouts should increase Government's process transparency, accountability, and efficiency [41]. The rollouts will also lay a foundation for the launch of e-governance, which could significantly enhance citizen participation in Government [41]. In 2019, an e-government service charter highlighting the noted e-government outcomes was launched in the Gauteng Province [41]. Per this launch, the province has focussed on improving internet connectivity, which forms one of the province's primary e-government facilitation priorities [41]. Initially, the Gauteng broadband network was launched in 2015 and saw the rolling out of 1 500km of fibre across the province. The three metropolitan municipalities in the province (i. e., the City of Ekurhuleni, the City of Tshwane and the City of Johannesburg) also laid a further 2 252km of fibre cable in the same year. Between 2015 and 2019, the Gauteng Province continued to implement various other e-government milestones; the most important of these, at least from an SMME perspective, were 1) the online central suppliers' database registration system, 2) the issuance of conservation permits, and 3) the ICT access registration for SMMEs [35].

Despite these initiatives, various challenges continue to be encountered with respect to e-government, which, in turn, affect the services, offered by SMMEs. These challenges are presented in more detail in the following paragraphs.

3. 6. E-government challenges in Gauteng

Challenges in the implementation of e-government

At the provincial level, the execution of e-government services for SMMEs has not been an easy or flawless process [41]. The province has and continues to face several hurdles, including poor coordination of strategies and programmes, a lack of adequate skills, poor buy-ins from key stakeholders, implementation efficiency issues, and general systems underutilisation [41]. These challenges, along with the solutions that the province has attempted to implement, form a key focus of this thesis. More specifically, this study views these challenges with respect to the extent, to which they adversely affect e-government implementation and trickle down to affect e-government uptake, use, and benefit to both SMMEs and the general citizenry.

Internal regulatory challenges

A major challenge, highlighted by the Gauteng e-Government Department, was the level of efficiency in resource utilisation [41]. In particular, the department's publicly available annual reports from 2015 to 2019 indicate patterns of misuse concerning financial resources. For example, in 2016, R39.2m of the department's expenditure was classified as 'irregular' by the Auditor General's office [41]. This figure then rose significantly in 2017, to R85.5m, then subsided back to around R32.7m in 2018, and then 31.9m in 2019 [41].

It should be noted, that the Auditor General's office defines 'irregular expenditure' as "spending, which had not been done within the prescripts of the laws, implying that in the process leading to the spending there complied with applicable laws [41]. While the office stresses that irregular expenditure does not automatically mean that funds have been abused and misappropriated, it further asserts that this term is generally associated with spending money outside of given legislative and strategic provisions [42]. On 8 April 2020, eNews carried an article, related to ongoing investigations, relating to an allegedly inappropriately issued e-government services tender for R30m in the department [34]. The presented information in this section, thus, highlights evidence of a general deterioration in financial accountability in the department.

Such deterioration exists despite how, in its 2019 annual report, the Gauteng e-Government Department stresses the importance of transparency, accountability, and integrity in the supply

chain processes, linked to e-government [39]. This reaffirmation of these values comes from the local government's realisation of how irregularities in e-government services supplies can detract the province from attaining its e-government-related objectives [39]. Irregular expenditure is also a worrisome affair in that it detracts governmental entities from reaching their broader strategic objectives [42]. Non-compliance with procurement practices and legislation, as a major contributor to irregular expenditure, further negatively affects service delivery, as it increases the risk of unqualified service providers being hired [42].

Intergovernmental coordination

Another internal challenge, captured in the Gauteng Province's report, relates to the coordination of e-government implementation strategies and stakeholders [43]. Specifically, the Gauteng Province notes that the implementation of e-government services has been conducted at a divisional level, where different divisions in the province have their independent systems [43]. The second level of implementation then involves the integration of systems between the local and provincial governmental levels, as each has independent systems and programmes [43]. For example, the two cities, as well as the provincial departments, were each in the process of rolling out uncoordinated or partially coordinated broadband networks during 2015/2016 [43]. This resulted in the duplication of activities and inefficient use of resources [43].

Intergovernmental coordination issues as policy challenges are highlighted further in the National e-Government Strategy and Roadmap [39], which is managed by the Electronic Communications and Transactions Act (ECTA 25 of 2002; RSA 2002). This Strategy offers e-government-related provincial governmental departments the roles and responsibilities of coordinating e-government development with and within municipalities, as "the function of the provincial administration in e-government is to harmonise the municipal and provincial e-government services with different departments and stakeholders, in addition to arranging for mass awareness and sensitisation on e-government" [39].

In light of this understanding, coordination is seen as an implementation rather than a policy formulation issue. Thus, there is a view that a coordinated e-government development and implementation approach could result in the provision of broader services and the preservation of resources for the benefit of SMMEs, residents, and other involved coordinating stakeholders [34]. In its attempts to redress coordination challenges between local and provincial government efforts, the province also introduced the e-Government Centre for Excellence and Municipality Support in 2017 [34].

Internal coordination issues

At a provincial level, internal coordination issues that have arisen have been mostly associated with the use of various and different systems that compromise interoperability [37]. The UN comments that in situations where governmental entities have various independent systems that cannot be easily and technologically linked together, high sunk costs may cripple e-government efforts [37]. Amongst its targets for the periods 2015–2019 and 2020–2025, captured in its e-government strategic plan, is the province's facilitation of seamless interoperability across systems [35]. In particular, the following frameworks and programmes have been adopted to ensure internal coordination in e-government implementation: adoption of the Governance of ICT Policy Framework, which is a national government policy to support the standardised development and deployment of digital systems; the formulation of the GCR ICT Norms and Standards to coordinate standards and expectations of digital technology development and deployment within the provincial government, and the formulation and implementation of GCR ICT CMF to support standardised digital systems risk management across the province's divisions [35].

Of note is that these systems are related to the development and deployment of coordination efforts within the province that have been supported by various programmes and activities [39]. For example, in 2019, the province was able to implement 32 different digital systems on a common platform that facilitates the sharing of information resources [39]. The department has also been able to partner with the Design and Validation Centre Testing Centre, a Johannesburg Centre for

Skills Engineering (JCSE), the University of the Witwatersrand, and Tshimologong in a bid to better facilitate software development and deployment to improve the quality and interoperability of its digital and e-government systems [39].

E-government and digital skills

Skills shortages and their effects on the development of e-government have been extensively discussed in the Gauteng Province's e-Government Department's annual statements, published between 2015 and 2019, as well as in its latest e-government strategy [35]. In addition, skills shortages have been recorded on the users' side, as users are often found to not be able to apply the given systems to their businesses [34]. To manage these kinds of skills challenges, the province coordinated with the JCSE in 2017 to facilitate user and staff training [34]. The Province also introduced community-based digital training initiatives that targeted both residents and small businesses, including the eKasi labs, which facilitated both access to and training on the utilisation of e-government services [39].

Low user uptake

A major recurring challenge concerning e-government adoption in the Gauteng Province is lower user buy-in and uptake of available services [39]. This low engagement has resulted in the perception that resources are being wasted in the development of underutilised e-government systems [39]. For example, in the Gauteng Province e-Government Department's Annual Report for 2017, services underutilisation was associated with a lack of information present amongst targeted users as well as various accessibility challenges. To increase e-government services uptake, therefore, the province embarked on several initiatives [39].

These initiatives included the deployment of 40 e-government services ambassadors who were responsible for informing and convincing residents and businesses alike to use the offered services [39]. The province also launched incentive programmes for users [39]. Youth-based training on the uses and benefits of e-government services for employment and business opportunity harnessing was, in addition, offered, with over 700 youth receiving such training in 2017 [39]. The introduction of the eKasi labs to support township residents and businesses in their use of digital systems was, furthermore, undertaken in a bid to increase e-government use uptake, while customer satisfaction surveys, related to e-government, have been conducted in 2017, 2018, and 2019 [39]. Aside from these endeavours, the province has also conducted e-government outreach programmes under the Ntirhisano brand, which included direct engagement with entrepreneurs [39]. In the province's 2018 annual report, increases in e-government usage were, subsequently, confirmed. However, these numbers were still on the low side when considering the province's large population (i. e., 733 411 users were registered for e-government offerings) [39]. In 2019, another 351 430 users were added [39].

Of further note is that while falling under 'cooperative governance', local and provincial governments are essentially independent, autonomous entities, each with their respective powers and jurisdiction [39]. E-government as a public administration paradigm has, however, generally challenged this state of existence [37] as the 'whole-government' approach, upon which the e-government paradigm is hinged, advocates for the integration of e-services from and across national, regional, and local government domains to most seamlessly benefit all citizens [37]. As a result, the existence and implementation of e-governance require new thinking concerning how seemingly independent, yet interdependent governmental spheres can be integrated to provide more comprehensive e-government services that have a greater likelihood of being utilised by the targeted beneficiaries.

5. Discussion

Based on the findings and information, stated under the framework, the study proposes various recommendations to improve the situation.

There should be an establishment of an intergovernmental SMME/LED and e-government coordination body that consists of all stakeholders, identified in the framework, that would spearhead the implementation of the suggested framework.

The enhancement of e-government portals should be considered to integrate various agencies and departments that are tasked with assisting SMMEs. (Note: these e-government portals would need to provide links to all stakeholders who offer different forms of support to SMMEs, with a clear description of these stakeholders' mandates, products, and services).

The development of stand-alone SMME/LED strategies should be aimed at addressing identified challenges. (Note: such strategies would need to be integrated with e-government plans as part of the improvement plan highlighted previously. Such a need is based on how SMME support strategies currently exist as piecemeal packages that are fragmented across multiple documents; thereby creating risks of inconsistencies in content).

Municipalities should consider the assurance of economies of scale in broadband expansion, with the benefits of improved internet access to SMMEs. (Note: such broadband expansion across the country would need to be managed under a single entity). In relation to this recommendation, it is suggested, that the local government sphere should focus on the development of user systems. It is envisaged by this study, that without the burden of developing physical infrastructure, municipalities could better focus their skills, energies, and resources on improving e-government and general digital systems effectiveness, while simultaneously marketing these systems to the intended users.

The expansion of e-government use should be enhanced that reaching out to businesses in municipalities in such a way as to increase their uptake of these systems – these could include publicity campaigns, such as those, carried out by the Gauteng Department of e-Government.

The regular monitoring and evaluation of e-government evolution and uses should be in place, which could assist in assessing the extent, to which e-government systems remain relevant and feasible for use by SMMEs and other intended beneficiaries. (Note: this recommendation takes note of the theoretical framework's (i.e., the sustainable e-government maturity model by Joshi and Islam (2018) view that e-government use relies on the extent, to which it has evolved to meet user needs).

The enhancement of agility accessibility as a way of increasing e-government use should be deliberated. This recommendation implies that implementors must take note of the diversities in SMMEs in their communities and design systems that cater for different forms of accessibility, complexity, and digital literacies.

The enhancement of the CoT's commitment to the NFLED (2018-2028) should be contemplated. Such needed commitment is given the city's respective coordination, skills, and financial resources challenges that are present in its LED initiatives. The NFLED's (2018-2028) LED enabling pillars, which are "funding, monitoring and evaluation, organisational and institutional structures, capacity development, planning, research and strategy" [44] speak directly to the challenges, presented in the study.

It is believed, that the skilful implementation of the given recommendations could significantly improve the country's SMME operating environment through increased use of e-government.

The study's main limitations included the inability to gain responses from CoT SMME senior-level participants, as they were busy preparing strategies to handle covid situation impacting on their organisational services.

An important development that emerged during the Covid-19 crisis was the generally rapid adaptation to online technologies as a way of ensuring business continuity. Local government services did not, however, adapt quickly to this particular coping mechanism. Future studies may, therefore, consider research that assesses the impact of Covid-19 on SMMEs, along with the significance of general e-government strategies to assist small businesses during states of emergencies and disasters.

6. Conclusion

E-government is viewed as a system that supports improved non-bureaucratic service delivery support and, therefore, offers a solution to the noted SMME-related challenges. The study, therefore, explores an important relationship that cuts across two dimensions, namely e-government and SMMEs, in an environment where SMMEs often fail and, in a similar environment, where the implementation of government programmes is characterised by many challenges. In this way, the present study targeted the provision of a framework that could be applied in better relating

the two dimensions and, most importantly, in highlighting how e-government might be better managed to most effectively benefit SMMEs and reduce their failure rates. The findings are expected to add value to the existing body of knowledge on both SMME challenges and e-government.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

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